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Clinical Rehabilitation

Comparison between customised foot orthoses and insole combined with the use of extracorporeal shock wave therapy in plantar fasciitis, medium-term follow-up results: a randomised controlled trial.

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the clinical results of custom-made foot orthoses versus placebo flat cushioning insoles combined with a programme of stretching exercises and extracorporeal shock wave therapy on pain and foot functionality in patients with plantar fasciitis.

Design and setting: A randomised controlled clinical trial and an active comparator with follow-up at six months. Faculty of Podiatry and Centre Clinical private of Physiotherapy.

Subjects and interventions: Patients with plantar fasciitis were randomly assigned to either group A, which received custom-made foot orthoses, or group B, which received placebo insoles. All the participants received active extracorporeal shock wave therapy and a physiotherapist performed stretching exercises of the posterior muscle chain. Recruitment period was from November 2019 to May 2020.

Main measures: The primary outcome was foot pain, measured by visual analog scale and the secondary outcome measures were recorded by Roles and Maudsley scores respectively, at the beginning and at 1 week, 1 month and 6 months.

Results: 83 patients were randomised: 41 into the control group; 42 into the experimental group. The mean (SD) visual analogue scale at baseline were Control 6.31 (1.69), Exp 5.27 (1.64); at four weeks 7.26 (2.77) and 0.32 (1.02); and at six months 7.52 (3.40) and 0.10 (0.63) ($P < 0.05$). The differences between the experimental group and the control group were statistically significant at one and six months.

Conclusion: Wearing a custom-made foot orthosis leads to a follow-up improvement in patients with plantar fasciitis. The custom-made foot orthoses reduced foot pain and improved foot functionality.

Keywords

Foot, orthoses, plantar fasciitis, shoe insoles, treatment, radial shock waves, combined modality therapy

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**Comparison between customised foot orthoses and insole combined
with the use of extracorporeal shock wave therapy in plantar
fasciitis, medium-term follow-up results: a randomised controlled
trial.**

Short running title; Customised foot orthoses in plantar fasciitis

For Peer Review

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Introduction

Different theories propose that plantar fasciitis is due to biomechanical disorders because of stress in the zone of the insertion of the fascia.¹⁻³ This fact has led to the use of insoles as a treatment, but these have not yet been well evaluated. The most accepted theory is that orthopaedic devices optimise the foot's biomechanical load, decrease the excessive pronation and unload the fascia in its origin to recreate the heel cushion.^{4,5} Numerous studies report beneficial results about the use of customised plantar orthotics and other studies defend treatment with exercise and stretching therapy with proper footwear and the use of orthotic supports.⁶⁻⁸ Molded foot orthoses are known to increase the stability of the foot, to reduce plantar fascia strain, and to change frontal plane and rearfoot alignment. Wearing foot orthotics improves, by a mechanical effect, the postural control by optimising the positioning of the foot. Studies do not exist which use the same insoles or the same materials. This hinders the comparison of studies. Foot orthoses have been used worldwide, and customised plantar supports are proposed as choice treatments in plantar fasciitis. However, there are few studies of treatment centred on customised plantar supports and foot physiotherapy.⁹⁻¹¹

This study aims at determining the clinical results of custom-made foot orthoses versus placebo flat cushioning insoles, combined with a programme of stretching exercises and extracorporeal shock wave therapy, for pain and foot functionality in patient with plantar fasciitis at medium-term follow-up. We examine the effects of foot orthosis intervention and we waited this length of time in order to confirm that spontaneous resolution did not occur, and that no improvement was achieved with simpler therapies.

Methods

The study was a double-blinded randomised controlled trial with a parallel-group design with follow-up at six months. It was carried out in accordance with the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki. The study was conducted in accordance with the Guideline for Good Clinical Practice. Ethics approval for the study was obtained from the Biomedical Research Ethics Committee (id: 2054-N-19) of the Andalusia Regional Government, registered at ClinicalTrials.gov (NCT04461197) and drawn up in accordance with the CONSORT statement guideline. There were no changes to the design after trial registration. The University of Seville was responsible for the integrity and conduct of the study. This study was non-funded, and the cost of orthosis materials was provided by the clinical unit. These institutions had no influence on the results. The participating patients were recruited from a private rehabilitation and physiotherapy and podiatry unit in Seville (Spain) by researchers who work in this centre and in the Faculty of Nursing, Physiotherapy and Podiatry of the University of Seville. The patients were recruited from this centre and the data were gathered in the same clinic unit. The recruitment period was November 2019 to May 2020. The patients were referred to the lead investigator and considered for participation in the study according to the inclusion criteria. The patients were diagnosed using a physical examination. The treatment plan was thoroughly explained to each patient in detail before the initiation of the study, and a written informed consent was obtained from each patient. Full protection of the participants' anonymity and of the data confidentiality was assured by the institution and by the personnel responsible for conducting the study.

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Inclusion criteria:

- Age over 18 years;
- Able to understand the explanations about the potential benefits and risks of participating in the study;
- Both genders;
- Diagnosis of chronic plantar fasciitis;
- Duration of symptoms equal or superior to 6 months at the time of enrollment;
- Foot Posture Index $\geq +6$ (pronated foot in one or both feet).

Exclusion criteria:

- Previous treatments with shock wave devices;
- Previous surgery on the painful heel, fasciotomy or heel spur surgery;
- History of calcaneus fracture;
- Any inflammation at the level of the ankle;
- Infection in the treated area;
- Patients with diabetes mellitus, cardiac, respiratory disease or Osteomyelitis;
- Patients on anticoagulant drugs;
- Pregnancy;
- Patients on immunosuppressive therapy;
- Rheumatoid arthritis or history of rheumatic disease;
- Neurological deficits;

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- Malignant disease with or without metastases;
- Significant liver function abnormalities;
- Neurological or vascular insufficiency in the painful heel;
- Discrepancy in the length of the foot > 5 mm; previous back of foot surgery;
- Patients treated with rigid plantar supports.

The patients were evaluated by an investigator to confirm the diagnosis of plantar fasciitis, including pain at the medial tubercle of the calcaneus associated with the plantar fascia origin without neuritic symptoms or signs of stress fracture, and the presence of pronated feet (Foot posture index $\geq +6$) rated ≥ 5 points on visual analogue scales. Patients with chronic plantar fasciitis were randomly assigned to the following two groups using a simple randomisation. The random assignment to each group was done by a collaborating researcher who established the sequence basing him/herself on a one-by one sequence generator, 1:1 ratio (the custom foot orthoses (group A) and the placebo insoles (group B). Group A was the experimental group and was given custom foot orthoses, while group B was the control group and received placebo insoles. All the participants received active radial extracorporeal shock wave therapy and a physiotherapist performed stretching exercises of the posterior muscle chain. The researcher who performed the measurements at 0 days, 1 week, 1 month and 6 months was not the same researcher who conducted the randomisation (M.C.J), performed the radial extracorporeal shock wave therapy (M.P.C), adapted the foot orthoses, and gave them to the participants (A.J.P.B). Thus, they were also blinded. This procedure is similar to others previously used by other studies.¹¹ The clinical variables were measured in person at the beginning of the study and via phone calls at other moments.

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Clinical data were collected including age, gender, weight, height, foot pain, and foot functionality. The variables measured were pain and foot functionality. The investigator who evaluated the clinical measurements was blinded to the allocated treatments. All the evaluations were repeated at the baseline and at each follow-up visit, 1 week and 1-month and 6 months after treatment by the same investigator. The patients were reevaluated in person by a researcher. Primary outcome measures were reduced pain and functional improvement. The duration of symptoms, visual analog scale and the Roles and Maudsley scores were recorded as secondary outcome measures. These have been validated as assessment tools for patients with heel pain.¹²

- Visual analogue scale (cm). The intensity of pain was measured on this scale. Heel pain intensity was referred to as 0–10, in which 0=no pain at all and 10= the worst pain possible. The patients are asked to mark the point that best represented their pain severity along the line and that point was measured on the 10-cm line using a ruler.
- Roles and Maudsley scale. This scale was used as a measure of the secondary result. This is a self-administered scale of functional valuation which classifies the patients into 4 categories.^{12,13} Some meta-analyses have used it to find out the quality of life of patients with plantar fasciitis, according to the pain, the limitation of movements and carrying out daily life activities. The score of 1 corresponds to a patient with an excellent quality of life (no symptoms, unlimited walking ability without pain, patient satisfied with the treatment outcome) and a score of 4 to a patient with the worst quality of life possible (inability to walk without severe pain, symptoms not improved or even worsened after treatment, patient not satisfied with the treatment outcome).
- Satisfaction's subjective scale. Additionally, the patients' satisfaction with

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3 the pain level during the treatment, as well as other treatments received
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5 afterwards were assessed. To estimate the subjective satisfaction a nominal
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7 scale with four possible answers (from 'absolutely satisfied' to
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9 'dissatisfied') was used to prevent the existence of a neutral (middle)
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11 position. The scale was applied at the end of the intervention. Patients
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13 received one questionnaire for each foot treated.
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17 Interventions with each participant were individually provided by trained
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19 podiatrists . Group A received custom foot orthoses and group B received placebo
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21 insoles. Orthotic insoles were provided for both groups, and daily plantar stretching
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23 exercises and gastrocnemius stretching were recommended. Also, the treatment protocol
24
25 includes 3 sessions of radial extracorporeal shock wave therapy^{14,15} using a STORZ
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27 MEDICAL Masterpuls MP 100 (Tägerwilten, Switzerland). All the patients received a
28
29 follow-up every week.¹⁶ Patient interaction with the devices in the other session was the
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31 same as in the first session.
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35 The foot orthoses for group A were custom made using phenolic foam molds of
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37 the feet. Separate molds were made of both feet for all the participants. The phenolic
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39 foam molds were made with the participants' feet supporting weight. The feet were
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41 manipulated before being put into the phenolic foam, placed in a neutral position. A
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43 positive mold of the feet was obtained filling the phenolic foam molds with liquid
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45 gypsum. The insole was made based on a positive mold of plaster with 45 Shore cork
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47 materials with horizontal thrusts just proximal to the metatarsal heads, with the intention
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49 of correcting the pathological subtalar pronation, with a 3mm bilateral raising of the
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51 heel and a bilateral latex metatarsal bar. All of this was lined with 3mm thick 30 shore
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53 ethyl vinyl acetate on its top side and fine microfibre fabric which allows a certain
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55 elasticity on the lower side. The insole was given to the patient 10 days after the first
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57 visit.
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3 For group B, a flat insole of polyester resin was made, fitting it to the foot's size,
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5 but not adapting it to the longitudinal arch of the foot, with the aim of not altering the
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7 patient's normal biomechanical function. This did not provide a therapeutic effect but
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9 still had the visual effect of a custom foot orthosis. If they felt any discomfort, the
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11 participants were instructed to return as soon as possible so that the appropriate
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13 adjustments could be made to the orthoses. Both types of foot orthoses were made with
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15 the same covering colour to reduce the risk of bias. The participants were told that the
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17 foot orthoses assigned had to be used seven days a week for a minimum of eight hours
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19 per day for six months. After the final evaluation, group B received the same type of
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21 custom-made foot orthoses given to group A, which were kept throughout the six
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23 months of the study by the staff of the Clinical Centre.
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28 The number of participants included in this study was determined based on the
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30 bibliography consulted and previous studies. Online G-Power 3.1.0 was the software
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32 used for the calculation of the sample size [®] (Franz Faul, Universität Kiel, Germany).
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34 This study is designed to detect changes in the size effect greater than 0.6 (medium size
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36 effect) for a comparison of measures between two independent samples, assuming a
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38 type I and II error of 0.05 and 0.2, respectively. The result was a minimum sample size
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40 of 72 participants. 10% more participants were enlisted in case of possible losses during
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42 the study.
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47 The IBM SPSS version 22 for Windows software package (IBM, Armonk, NY,
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49 USA) and Excel were used for the statistical analysis. Data exploration was carried out,
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51 generating summary statistics for all the cases. This procedure is used to identify
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53 atypical or extreme values and characterise differences between case groups. Likewise,
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55 it enables identifying if the statistical techniques considered are appropriate and
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57 indicates the need to transform the data or use non-parametric tests. The numeric
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59 variables (quantitative) are summarised with averages and standard deviations or, in the
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3 case of very asymmetric distributions, means and percentiles (P25 and P75), while the
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5 non-numeric variables (qualitative) used frequencies and percentages. The Kolmogorov-
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7 Smirnov test was applied to determine the distribution of the variables. A descriptive
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9 statistic was done for the variables age, sex, and body mass index. The numerical variables
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11 were expressed in the form of averages and standard deviations. The data were
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13 evaluated on an intention-to-treat basis. The T Student test was used for the comparison
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15 between the averages of the groups, both in the VAS and in the RM scale. When a
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17 normal distribution pattern was rejected, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test was
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19 applied. The secondary results were evaluated to detect differences via the Chi2 tests for
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21 qualitative variables. The effect size was calculated using Cohen's D or eta squared. The
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23 analysis was done on an intention-to-treat basis and a value of $p < .05$ was established as
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25 statistically significant.
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30 Results

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32 **After signing an informed consent, the eighty-three participants were randomly**
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34 **allocated to the two groups.** Eighty-eight patients fulfilled the inclusion criteria and
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36 were included in this study. Four patients withdrew from the study during the treatment
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38 period, three patients could not complete the follow-up examination one month after
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40 treatment, and four patients rejected the study, informing that their symptoms had
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42 completely improved. The data of the lost patients were not included in the analysis.
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44 Finally, 76 patients with plantar fasciitis (Forty-one females and thirty-five males) were
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46 analysed, 39 in the experimental group and 37 in the control group (Figure 1).
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51 The baseline characteristics of the 76 participants included and analyzed in the study are
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53 presented in Table 1. The initial conditions of the two groups and of the whole of the
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55 sample were analysed. There were statistically significant differences in the baseline
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57 characteristics, such as age with a p value of 0.001 and Body Mass Index with a p value
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59 of .003.
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3 By sex, the total sample was 41 (53.9 %) females and 35 (46.1%) males. The average
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5 age of the participants was 36.5 ± 2.46 years (group A: 32.83 ± 1.84 years / group B:
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7 41.89 ± 1.65 years), with a p value of 0.001. The Body Mass Index (BMI) average of the
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9 sample was 25.81 ± 2.70 (group A: 24.27 ± 2.58 / group B: 27.43 ± 1.70), with a p value of
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11 .001. ANCOVA is performed to determine the influence of the BMI (covariance) on the
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13 treatment. BMI does not influence the model ($p = 0.983$). The sample starts from the same
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15 conditions with respect to the pain's duration and the participants' gender. Only two adverse
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17 effects motivated by the therapy were reported. There were differences between the groups
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19 when compared with respect to the pain at the beginning of the treatment, after a month and
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21 after six months (Table 2-3). After carrying out the Student T test for independent samples, a
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23 value of significance for the visual analogue scale of less than .05 was obtained at all the
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25 moments of valuation, except a week later after applying shock waves. This value represents a
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27 significant difference in the average of the patients with PF who used the simultaneous
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29 treatment of shock waves and stretches and plantar supports versus treatment of shock waves
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31 and stretches of the posterior muscle chain. On the other hand, with respect to the Roles and
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33 Maudsley scale, significant differences were observed in all the measurements ($p = .001$) related
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35 with petechiae in the zone of application. The global data of the sample, and disaggregated by
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37 groups, inform as to the pain.
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41 42 Discussion

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45 In this randomised study, we compared customised foot orthoses and insoles combined
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47 with a programme of stretches in plantar fasciitis treatment. To the best of our
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49 knowledge, this is the first study that has evaluated this therapy via a medium-term
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51 follow-up. The treatment of plantar fasciopathy is a challenge for health care
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53 professionals. In this study, there were no statistically significant differences between
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55 the groups according to the visual analogue scale and the Roles Maudsley score after
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57 one week. However, the differences between the experimental group and the control
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3 group were statistically significant at the one- and six-month follow-up, in favour of the
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5 experimental group. It is also interesting to note that although the mean results were
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7 good one week after the treatment, the number of patients who did not develop
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9 therapeutic improvement was higher than in the experimental group. Our results show
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11 that the people who wore a custom-made orthosis did better than those who were given
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13 an insole for their treatment. This confirms the published data about custom-made foot
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15 orthoses in plantar fasciitis patients.⁵

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19 The pain was chosen as the main outcome measure because all the patients with plantar
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21 fasciitis experience pain and this is strongly related to functionality. The major concern
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23 of patients is to improve the chronic pain which they suffer from. Therefore, this must
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25 be any treatment's main aim. In our study, the pain was evaluated according to a visual
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27 analogue scale at the medium term: before, after a week, after a month and after 6
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29 months. Other studies have evaluated this, with more subjective scales, showing the
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31 same significant improvements in pain reduction and of quality of life.¹¹ The pain
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33 reduction was statistically significant in both groups. Our results showed improvement
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35 in pain reduction at the medium-term follow-up. However, the placebo group showed a
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37 worsening of the clinical symptomology of pain after the 6-month follow-up. We found
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39 that the average pain intensity decreased from 6.31 ± 1.69 to 3.59 ± 2.19 in the control
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41 group and from 5.27 ± 1.64 to 2.6 ± 1.54 in the treatment group immediately after the
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43 orthosis application. This was further reduced to 0.32 ± 1.02 and to 0.10 ± 0.63 in the
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45 experimental group after one and six months of treatment, respectively. On the contrary,
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47 this increased more than at the beginning in the control group after one and six months
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49 of treatment. These results are consistent with the findings of previous studies which
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51 supported that orthotic treatment was effective for alleviating footpain.^{8,9,14,17,18}

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53 Although the subjects who wore a flat insole reported reduced pain intensity, the
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55 intervention effect was more prominent for customised foot orthoses (Table 2). This
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301 implied that even a flat insole could decrease pain after one week. The insole used for
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302 our control condition was made of shock absorbent EVA materials, which probably
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303 aided in reducing pain. This hypothesis nevertheless needs further exploration.
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304 In several studies,¹⁹⁻²² it was admitted that plantar orthoses allowed a significant pain
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305 regression in plantar fasciitis as indicated by the decreased visual analogue scale score.
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306 This scale has been used as an evaluation scale in almost all studies of plantar fasciitis.¹¹
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307 But our results differ from those of a systematic review done by Landorf et al.,²³ where
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308 it was admitted that custom-made insoles may improve function but not pain, after 3
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309 months in people with plantar heel pain compared with a sham orthosis, but these may
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310 be no better than appropriate prefabricated orthoses. In this line, several clinical trials
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311 have shown improvement in foot pain with the use of this type of foot orthoses and a
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312 customised insole that provide foot functional control, but there is no consensus on the
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313 most successful conservative treatment. Other studies reported the importance of
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314 biomechanical correction with plantar supports and the use of proper footwear for the
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315 effective treatment of plantar fasciitis.²⁴ According to Xu et al.²⁵ there was no
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316 significant difference of plantar foot comfort in plantar fasciitis between the customised
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317 foot orthoses 3D group and the orthopedic insoles group ($P>0.05$). After 8 weeks, all
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318 groups reported more comfort compared with the same group in week 0 ($P<0.05$). The
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319 comfort scores reported by the experimental group were significantly lower than those
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320 of the control group ($P<0.05$).²⁵ In our study, custom-made foot orthoses were adapted
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321 to a foot cast that reflected better foot posture and comfort is also a factor affecting the
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322 use of the foot orthosis. Those patients improve thanks to the use of customised foot
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323 orthoses which are designed based on biomechanical principles that relax the stress of
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324 the plantar arch, especially when they are standing for a long time, alleviating the pain
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325 and improving the foot's stability. It has been well documented that custom foot
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326 orthoses have an effect on reducing the thickness of the plantar fascia in people with

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337 plantar fasciopathy.²² However, the experimental group improved to a greater extent,
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338 demonstrating the clinical effectiveness of the foot orthosis. In the study published by
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339 Wrobel et al.,⁹ the comparison between custom foot orthoses, prefabricated foot
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340 orthoses and sham insoles in plantar fasciitis treatment showed that all three groups
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341 improved in morning pain after treatment that included standardised athletic shoes,
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342 stretching and ice. Their results showed improvements of pain for the revised foot
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343 function index score, as well as for the programme of stretching exercises recommended
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344 to their patients. Customised insoles provided foot functional control. This fact
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345 reinforces our hypothesis about the importance of treatment via plantar supports for
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346 positive results in solving plantar fasciitis.²⁵ In other studies,²⁶ custom made foot
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347 orthoses were used versus a combined treatment of manipulation and mobilisation of the
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348 foot and stretching exercises. Grim et al. reported that manual therapy and a customised
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349 insole reduce pain and that manual therapy alone is what shows more benefits, contrary
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350 to the results obtained in our study.²⁶ All three treatments showed statistically
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351 significant ($p < 0.01$) improvements in both scales at the baseline and at the follow-up
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352 sessions after 1 month. However, the manual therapy group showed greater
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353 improvements than both the other groups ($p < 0.01$).

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354 Based on previous studies' conclusions that a programme of stretches reduces the heel
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355 pain caused by plantar fasciitis,^{16,27} we believe that both combined therapies were
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356 effective in this study. Unlike the study published by Riel et al.²⁸, there were no
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357 differences between the groups with different exercises in terms of pain. Our protocol
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358 was completed by carrying out a programme of stretches that included flexibility of the
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359 plantar fascia, calf–Achilles complex and hamstrings, intrinsic foot muscle
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360 strengthening exercises, balance and proprioception training exercises, and calf
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361 strengthening exercises. The stretching of the plantar fascia is more effective than that
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362 of the Achilles tendon in the reduction of the pain and the functional recuperation. We

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353 determined the clinic results with customised plantar supports versus a placebo insole
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354 combined with a programme of exercises. This is why this research means to help other
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355 researchers and foot and ankle clinicians in the choice of the best treatment for this
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356 pathology.

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357 The secondary outcome measure was determined by the Roles Maudsley scale.^{12,13}
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358 Significant differences were not found between the groups at the baseline and after one
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359 week, but there were significant differences between both groups after one and six
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360 months. The intervention of pain according to the Roles Maudsley scale was reduced
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361 statistically significant in the experimental group. Our results show differences in the
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362 valuation of the pain and the quality of life of patients with plantar fasciitis. The mean
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363 visual analogue scale and the Roles Maudsley scores were statistically improved six
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28
364 months after the treatment. We believe that in this study extracorporeal shock wave
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365 therapy showed an effectiveness in plantar fasciitis with favourable short-term
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366 effects.^{29,30} In the meta-analysis done by Sun et al.,³¹ it was admitted that extracorporeal
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367 shock wave therapy reduced pain as indicated by the decreased Roles and Maudsley
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368 scale, and brought about an earlier incorporation into their daily life activities and less
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369 complications.³¹ This is a non-invasive treatment modality used in sports and
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370 musculoskeletal medicine, and in present clinical foot and ankle practice. Nevertheless,
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371 the effectiveness of the long-term treatment is determined by the use of plantar supports
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372 which correct the plantar fasciitis biomechanical etiology. In our opinion, an important
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373 finding to highlight in this study is that the medium-term follow-up results with custom-
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374 made foot orthoses provide improvement in patients with plantar fasciitis. In our study,
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375 the patients used insoles made to the measure of their feet's molds, which enables them
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376 to adapt them to their usual footwear and which improved their pain, foot health and
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377 their health in general.
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Another important finding of our study was the significant improvement in the experimental group with customised plantar supports which receives extracorporeal shock wave treatment associated with stretching exercises, this being combined, in contrast with the placebo group. Other studies observed that the combination of extracorporeal shock wave therapy and stretches is very effective when combined.^{29,32} Previously, Yan et al.³³ carried out an evaluation of the effectiveness of extracorporeal shock wave therapy and custom foot orthoses, together and separately, informing of significant improvements of pain for the three modalities of treatment. The visual analogue scores in the 3 groups were all reduced after the treatment compared with the corresponding scores before the therapy ($P < 0.05$). In 2019, Çağlar-Okur and Aydın,¹¹ compared extracorporeal shock wave therapy with custom foot orthotics. They observed that neither method was superior in treating plantar fasciitis. They found a significant improvement in the custom foot orthotics group at 48 weeks compared with that in the extracorporeal shock wave therapy group. Both groups achieved significant improvements in morning pain at 4, 12 and 24 weeks compared with their baseline values ($P < 0.001$), and a significant continued improvement was observed in the custom foot orthotics group at 48 weeks ($P < 0.05$). The custom-made foot orthoses reduced foot pain significantly in plantar fasciitis. According to the literature, the number of studies comparing different treatments have been quite limited. Scientific evidence exists about the different therapeutic alternatives for plantar fasciitis, but there is not a clear consensus about how to solve this condition.^{6,7} Numerous studies apply different conservative treatments, combined and on their own, but the majority concentrate on therapeutic strategies to decrease the pain and improve their effectiveness.^{13,16}

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This study has several strengths and limitations. The results from this study add to the growing number of favourable reports in treating chronic plantar fasciitis. In support of our findings, there are a few points to be noted. Firstly, a follow-up of the

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3 patients has been done until 6 months. With respect to the sex, the sample is homogeneous,
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5 which enables us to find out the behaviour and differences by sex. Another strength of this study
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7 is that various methods have been used in the conservative treatment though there is not
8
9 currently a consensus about the most successful treatment.
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13 There were, however, several limitations in the current study design. We did not
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15 include biomechanical outcome measurements in this study, which limited the
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17 interpretation of the pain control mechanism in our orthotic intervention. Lastly, another
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19 limitation could be that the patients have significant differences in age and BMI. These
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21 are two factors to take into account when interpreting the data. The BMI has a direct
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23 relation with the pathological process of pronation. Also, the exact number of hours that
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25 the patients wore the orthotics cannot be confirmed. The control group started with
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27 greater pain than the experimental group. However, the use of shock waves caused both
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29 groups to improve within a week. Therefore, pain differences were controlled.
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35 Wearing a custom-made foot orthosis leads to an improvement at the medium-
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37 term follow-up in patients with plantar fasciitis. The combination of treatments is more
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39 effective than one on its own. This modality of treatment is effective in pain reduction
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41 and improves the foot's functionality. The custom-made foot orthoses combined with a
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43 programme of stretches and extracorporeal shock wave therapy significantly reduced
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45 foot pain and functionality.
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47 48 **Clinical messages**

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50 -The medium-term follow-up results with custom-made foot orthoses provide
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52 improvement in patient with plantar fasciitis.
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55 - There are differences between the groups with respect to the pain at the
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57 beginning of the treatment, after a month and after six months.
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For Peer Review

Fig. 1. CONSORT diagram showing the flow of PF participants through each stage of the randomised trial.

Table 1. Socio-demographic: Mean, and standard deviation data patients of the sample.

Characteristic	Total group (N=76)	Group A (n=39) (custom foot orthoses +Stretches of the posterior muscle chain + extracorporeal shock wave therapy)	Group B (n=37) (placebo insole + Stretches of the posterior muscle chain + extracorporeal shock wave therapy)	P- value
Age				
Mean ±SD	36.5±2.46	32.83±1.84	41.89±1,65	.001 ^a
Sex				
Female	54%(n=41)	54%(n=21)	54%(n=20)	
Male	46%(n=35)	46%(n=18)	46%(n=17)	.342 ^b
BMI (Kg/m²)	25.81±2.70	24.27±2.58	27.43±1.10	.001 ^c
Pain duration (Months)				
Mean ±SD	16.7±2.46	18.3±1.22	14.7±3.46	.162 ^c

Abbreviations. BMI: body mass index; ESWT: extracorporeal shock wave therapy, SD: Standard deviation. ^a Mann-Whitney U Test, ^b Test Chi ², ^c Student T Test

Table 2. Comparison between the experimental and control groups in the visual analog scale and the initial Roles and Maudsley scale

VAS (N= 76)		Baseline	1 st week	1 st month	6 th month
Experimental Group (n=39)	Mean ±SD	5.73±1.73	3.04±1.91	3.41±4.00	3.29±4.26
	CI 95%	5.3-6.1	2.6-3.5	2.5-4.4	2.3-4.3
	Mean ±SD	5.27±1.64	2.6±1.54	0,32±1,02	0,10±0,63
	CI 95%	4.7-5.8	2.1-3.1	0.0-0.7	0.1-0.3
Control Group (n=37)	Mean ±SD	6.31±1.69	3.59±2.19	7.26 ±2.77	7.52±3.40
	CI 95%	5.7-6.9	2.8-4.4	6.3-8.3	6.1-8.5
	Significance (P value)	0.010**	0.081	0.0001***	0.0001***
	Effect size	0.58&	0.60&	3.37 ^s	3.46 ^s
Roles & Maudsley		Baseline	1 st week	1 st month	6 th month
Overall (n= 76)	Poor % (n)	62.5 (n=45)	8.3 (n=6)	31.9 (n=23)	36.1(n=26)
	Acceptable % (n)	37.5 (n=27)	15.3 (n=11)	8.3 (n=6)	2.8 (n=2)
	Good % (n)	0.0 (n=0)	76.4 (n=55)	11.1 (n=8)	0.0 (n=0)
	Excellent % (n)	0.0 (n=0)	0.0 (n=0)	0.0 (n=35)	61.1 (n=44)
Experimental Group (n=39)	Poor % (n)	47.5 (n=18)	2.5 (n=1)	2.5 (n=1)	0.0 (n=0)
	Acceptable % (n)	52.5 (n=21)	2.5 (n=1)	12.5 (n=5)	2.5 (n=1)
	Good % (n)	0.0 (n=0)	95.0 (n=37)	85.0 (n=33)	0.0 (n=0)
	Excellent % (n)	0.0 (n=0)	0.0 (n=0)	0.0 (n=0)	97.5 (n=38)
Control Group (n=37)	Poor % (n)	81.3(n=30)	15.2(n=5)	71.9(n=27)	81.3(n=30)
	Acceptable % (n)	18.8 (n=7)	31.3 (n=12)	15.5 (n=6)	3.1 (n=1)
	Good % (n)	0.0 (n=0)	53.1 (n=20)	9.4 (n=3)	0.0 (n=0)
	Excellent % (n)	0.0 (n=0)	0.0 (n=0)	3.1 (n=1)	15.6 (n=6)
	Significance (P value)	0.006**	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***
	Effect size	.326&	.509&	.874 ^s	.875 ^s

Abbreviations. SD: standard deviation; CI: confidence Interval Effect size.; &: small ES; &: medium ES; S: large ES.
Significance set at p < 0.05. * p < 0,05; ** p < 0,01; *** p < 0,001.

CONSORT 2010 checklist of information to include when reporting a randomised trial*

Section/Topic	Item No	Checklist item	Reported on page No
Title and abstract			
	1a	Identification as a randomised trial in the title	1
	1b	Structured summary of trial design, methods, results, and conclusions (for specific guidance see CONSORT for abstracts)	2
Introduction			
Background and objectives	2a	Scientific background and explanation of rationale	3
	2b	Specific objectives or hypotheses	3
Methods			
Trial design	3a	Description of trial design (such as parallel, factorial) including allocation ratio	4
	3b	Important changes to methods after trial commencement (such as eligibility criteria), with reasons	4
Participants	4a	Eligibility criteria for participants	5
	4b	Settings and locations where the data were collected	4
Interventions	5	The interventions for each group with sufficient details to allow replication, including how and when they were actually administered	6-8
Outcomes	6a	Completely defined pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures, including how and when they were assessed	6-9
	6b	Any changes to trial outcomes after the trial commenced, with reasons	4
Sample size	7a	How sample size was determined	10
	7b	When applicable, explanation of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines	Not applicable
Randomisation:			
Sequence generation	8a	Method used to generate the random allocation sequence	6
	8b	Type of randomisation; details of any restriction (such as blocking and block size)	6
Allocation concealment mechanism	9	Mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence (such as sequentially numbered containers), describing any steps taken to conceal the sequence until interventions were assigned	6
Implementation	10	Who generated the random allocation sequence, who enrolled participants, and who assigned participants to interventions	6

1	Blinding	11a	If done, who was blinded after assignment to interventions (for example, participants, care providers, those assessing outcomes) and how	4
2				
3		11b	If relevant, description of the similarity of interventions	
4	Statistical methods	12a	Statistical methods used to compare groups for primary and secondary outcomes	10
5		12b	Methods for additional analyses, such as subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses	10
6				
7	Results			
8	Participant flow (a	13a	For each group, the numbers of participants who were randomly assigned, received intended treatment, and	6
9	diagram is strongly		were analysed for the primary outcome	
10	recommended)	13b	For each group, losses and exclusions after randomisation, together with reasons	4
11	Recruitment	14a	Dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up	5
12		14b	Why the trial ended or was stopped	Not applicable
13				
14	Baseline data	15	A table showing baseline demographic and clinical characteristics for each group	Table 1
15	Numbers analysed	16	For each group, number of participants (denominator) included in each analysis and whether the analysis was	10-11
16			by original assigned groups	
17				
18	Outcomes and	17a	For each primary and secondary outcome, results for each group, and the estimated effect size and its	10-11
19	estimation		precision (such as 95% confidence interval)	
20		17b	For binary outcomes, presentation of both absolute and relative effect sizes is recommended	Not applicable
21	Ancillary analyses	18	Results of any other analyses performed, including subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses, distinguishing	10-11
22			pre-specified from exploratory	
23				
24	Harms	19	All important harms or unintended effects in each group (for specific guidance see CONSORT for harms)	10-11
25				
26	Discussion			
27	Limitations	20	Trial limitations, addressing sources of potential bias, imprecision, and, if relevant, multiplicity of analyses	16-17
28	Generalisability	21	Generalisability (external validity, applicability) of the trial findings	11
29	Interpretation	22	Interpretation consistent with results, balancing benefits and harms, and considering other relevant evidence	12-16
30				
31	Other information			
32	Registration	23	Registration number and name of trial registry	4
33	Protocol	24	Where the full trial protocol can be accessed, if available	4
34	Funding	25	Sources of funding and other support (such as supply of drugs), role of funders	17
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39 *We strongly recommend reading this statement in conjunction with the CONSORT 2010 Explanation and Elaboration for important clarifications on all the items. If relevant, we also
40 recommend reading CONSORT extensions for cluster randomised trials, non-inferiority and equivalence trials, non-pharmacological treatments, herbal interventions, and pragmatic trials.
41 Additional extensions are forthcoming: for those and for up to date references relevant to this checklist, see www.consort-statement.org.
42